

Metal Ion Interactions with Nucleic Acid Base Pairs in Solution – A Potentiometric Study

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The formation of bio-ligand chelates of some divalent transition metal ions, viz. Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} with adenine as primary ligand (A) and 5-fluorouracil as the secondary ligand (L) has been carried out pH-metrically at 25° and at a constant ionic strength, $\mu = 0.1 M$ ($NaNO_3$). The stability constants of binary MA and ternary MAL complexes, where $M = Mn^{II}$, Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} , A = adenine and L = 5-fluorouracil, have been determined using a modified Irving-Rossotti technique and found to follow the Irving-Williams trend. In all the cases, Co^{II} has minimum and Cu^{II} has maximum stability and all the mixed ligand complexes have been found to be less stable than the binary metal-5-fluorouracil complexes except Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} , while it is more stable than metal-adenine binary complexes.

The interaction of transition metal ions with nucleic acid constituents has become an interesting area of studies due to their biological significance¹ and potential chemotherapeutic properties². Though considerable work has been reported on the complexes of ligands of biological significance with a number of cations in solid³ and on the formation of binary and ternary complexes⁴⁻⁶, a scanty work appears to have been done in the area of mixed ligand complexes involving base pairs and mispairs⁷. Hence, it is of interest to gain an insight into the nature of metal-complexation of purine and pyrimidine base pairs in solution and the present paper describes a potentiometric study of

the binary and ternary complex formation of some divalent biologically essential transition metal ions, viz., Mn, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn and Cd with 6-aminopurine (adenine : ADN) and 2,4-dihydroxy-5-fluoropyrimidine (5-fluorouracil : 5-FU) individually and with 6-aminopurine-2,4-dihydroxypyrimidine (adenine-5-fluorouracil) base pair.

Results and Discussion

Binary systems :

Proton-ligand systems : Fig. 1a shows that in the initial stages of the titration where the medium is strongly acidic, the proton-ligand curves shift above or below the acid

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration curves for binary and ternary $M(II)$ complexes : (a) H^+ -ligand, (b) $M(II)$ -ADN, (c) $M(II)$ -5-FU and (d) $M(II)$ -ADN-5-FU systems.

curve due to protonation or deprotonation of the ligand used.

H⁺-ADN system : Adenine (ADN) is quite basic and considered to exist in the amino form rather than imino. The probable protonation site in ADN is N₁ or C₆-NH₂. The protonation of ADN in acidic medium starts at pH 3.0 (V = 0; V is the volume of NaOH used) as it accepts proton from the medium resulting in an increase in pH and consequently proton-ADN curve (Fig. 1a) shifts to the left (or above) of the acid curve. The pK₁ value of ADN has been determined to be 4.03 under the experimental conditions and supported by earlier works⁸ where the values reported are in the range 3.5–4.2. This is associated with protonation from the protonated form of ADN (*cf.* protonated aniline, pK = 4.6) and the protonation site is most likely C₆-NH₃⁺ group. But thereafter several studies have proved that ⁺N₁H group is the site of proton ionisation (pK ~ 4.0) and the value of pK₂ is 9.73 suggesting that the proton ionisation from neutral ADN (pK~10.0) is from N₉H group⁴. ADN has one dissociable proton as it is evident from the proton-ADN formation curve (figure not shown) exhibiting a wave-like shape with one distinct step at pH~7.0. Protonation constant values are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROTONATION CONSTANTS OF PURINE AND PYRIMIDINE DERIVATIVES

Temp. = 25°, μ = 0.1 M (NaNO₃)

Ligand	log K ₁ ^H		log K ₂ ^H	
	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
ADN	9.73 ± 0.03	9.70	4.03 ± 0.06	4.10
5-FU	10.65 ± 0.01	10.93	7.85 ± 0.01	7.84

H⁺-5FU system : Pyrimidines are weak acids and uracil as well as 5-halouracils both have diketo (dilactam) structure which predominates in the solid as well as in solution. Thus, 5-halouracils theoretically have two ionisable protons. The pK₁ and pK₂ values determined for 5-fluorouracil (5-FU) are 7.85 and 10.65 respectively, which are in good agreement with the values reported by other workers⁹. The presence of electron-withdrawing halogen

(F) group at 5-position exerts an inductive as well as mesomeric effect and consequently results in lower deprotonation (dissociation) constant (pK) values (*cf.* uracil, pK₁ = 9.45). The formation curve of 5-FU (figure not shown) exhibits a wave-like shape showing two distinct steps at pH ~7.0 and ~10.0 corresponding to the protonation of oxo groups of the ligand (5-FU).

M-Ligand (1 : 1) complexing systems : From the titration curves A, B, C, D and E, the number of protons bound per free ligand ion (\bar{n}_A), deprotonation constant values (pK₁, pK₂) (Table 1), average number of ligands attached per metal ion (\bar{n}) and free ligand exponents (pL) for primary (adenine/ADN : A) as well as secondary (5-fluorouracil/5-Fu : L) ligands at different pH-values were evaluated using modified Irving-Rossotti procedure^{10,11}. The formation curves corresponding to metal-ADN and metal-5-FU were then plotted (figures not shown). Approximate values of the formation constants obtained by interpolation to half- \bar{n}_A (\bar{n}) value method (a) and determined by the average value method (b) are recorded in Table 2.

M-ADN-systems : It is evident from the Fig. 1 that the titration curves obtained for the six metal ions and ADN as primary ligand (A), curve-C (Fig. 1b) diverges from the ADN curve (Fig.1a) in the pH range 3.0–5.0 where a 1 : 1 (M : A) complex is formed and remains stable upto pH 7.0. The additional amount of alkali consumed above pH 7.0 may be due to formation of hydroxo complexes⁵, which completes at around pH 9.0 except Cu^{II} which precipitates out at pH 5.0–6.0. The stabilities of M-ADN complexes (Table 2) follows the trend : Mn^{II} > Co^{II} < Ni^{II} << Cu^{II} >> Zn^{II} < Cd^{II}, which is in conformity with the Irving-William's order^{12,13} and the absence of protonated and polynuclear species was confirmed by using several concentrations of reactants and the results obtained were identical.

M : 5-FU systems : Titration curves (E) obtained for all the six metal ions and 5-FU as a secondary ligand (L) (Fig. 1c) departs from the 5-FU curve (Fig. 1a) in the pH range 2.5–5.0 except Co^{II} (at pH 8.6), where a 1 : 1 metal-ligand complexation occurs and completes at around pH 7.0. The formation of hydroxo complexes of such systems occur at

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF BINARY AND TERNARY METAL COMPLEXES AND COMPARISON OF log K VALUES

Temp. 25°, μ = 0.1 M (NaNO₃)

Cation	Primary ligand (A)		Secondary ligand (L)		Mixed ligand (A.L)		log K _{MAL} ^{ML*}	
	log K _{MA} ^{M(a)}	log K _{MA} ^{M(b)}	log K _{ML} ^{M(a)}	log K _{ML} ^{M(b)}	log K _{MAL} ^{MA(a)}	log K _{MAL} ^{MA(b)}	Method (a)	Method (b)
Mn ^{II}	4.250 0	5.264 3	6.487 5	8.156 2	6.150 0	7.948 0	-0.337 5	-0.208 2
Co ^{II}	4.516 7	4.249 8	5.000 0	6.178 6	5.166 7	5.500 3	0.166 7	-0.678 3
Ni ^{II}	5.316 7	4.342 0	5.116 7	7.104 5	6.216 7	5.913 1	1.100 0	-1.191 4
Cu ^{II}	7.633 3	8.229 0	8.083 3	8.373 9	9.883 3	8.687 0	1.800 0	0.313 1
Zn ^{II}	5.766 7	5.319 6	6.100 0	7.171 0	7.016 7	6.980 4	0.916 7	-0.190 6
Cd ^{II}	5.600 0	5.980 3	5.800 0	7.057 3	6.150 0	7.686 3	0.350 0	0.629 0

Method (a) : interpolation to half \bar{n} value. Method (b) : average value method. *log K_{MAL}^{ML} = log K_{MAL}^{MA} - log K_{ML}^M.

pH 7.0–9.0 as usual except Cu^{II} which precipitates out at pH 6.0–7.0. The order of stability of 1 : 1 : : M : 5-FU complexes (Table 2) is : $\text{Mn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Co}^{\text{II}} < \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} < \text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cd}^{\text{II}}$, which is again in conformity with the Irving-William's order.

In the binary M-L systems, Cu^{II} forms both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes^{6,14}, while other metal ions form only 1 : 1 complexes. In all the binary systems, 1 : 1 (M : L) complexes were studied and 1 : 2 complex species could not be examined due to precipitation/opacity/turbidity. Also, the values of $\log K_1$ (K_1 is first step formation constant in M : L systems) for various complexes other than Cu^{II} are fairly close to each other. The evaluated stabilities of Cu^{II} complexes are usually higher than that could be expected from ionic radius or electronegativity considerations¹⁵. The additional stability of the Cu^{II} complexes may be attributed to the unique electronic configuration (d^9) of Cu^{II} ion which is capable of additional stabilisation due to Jahn-Teller distortion^{13,16}.

Further, it has been observed that M : 5-FU complexes are quite stable (2–3 log units; cf. Table 2) than that of M : ADN complexes.

Ternary system :

The mixed ligand titration curve (ADN-5FU-M) for all the six metal ions (F) initially overlaps with M-ADN curve upto pH 7.0 and then departs from the secondary ligand titration curve (D) only after the complete formation of 1 : 1 $[\text{M-ADN}]^+$ species and always remains lower than the M-ADN curve except Cu^{II} which again shows an exceptional behaviour as the corresponding ADN-5FU-M curve lies above the M-ADN curve. This is only because when the formation of 1 : 1 : : M : A is complete, the combination of L to MA takes place and additional amount of alkali is required to neutralise the liberated proton due to the formation of mixed ligand complex M : A : L. Turbidity as well as precipitation occurs between pH 7.0 and 9.0 as a consequence of formation of hydroxo species as discussed earlier in binary M-L systems.

It may thus be assumed that the secondary ligand 5-FU would combine with $[\text{M-ADN}]^+$ complex in ternary systems similarly as it does with $[\text{M}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]^{2+}$ species in the binary systems. Thus, the average number of secondary ligand molecules attached per MA ions (\bar{n}_{mix}) and free ligand exponent (pL_{mix}) at different pH-values were evaluated similarly as in the binary systems using modified Irving-Rossotti equation. Formation curves corresponding to various mixed ligand systems were obtained by plotting \bar{n}_{mix} against pL_{mix} (figure not shown) and the corresponding formation constants obtained by average value method as well as by interpolating to half- \bar{n}_{mix} value, are recorded in Table 2. The order of stability constants of mixed ligand complexes is $\text{Mn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Co}^{\text{II}} < \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} \ll \text{Cu}^{\text{II}} \gg \text{Zn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Cd}^{\text{II}}$.

From statistical considerations, the stabilities of ternary complexes (M : ADN : 5-FU) should be appreciably lower than the first step formation constant of M : 5-FU as the

concentration of electrons around the metal ions in $[\text{M-ADN}]^+$ systems would be more than in $[\text{M}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]^{2+}$ owing to ADN being more strongly coordinating than H_2O . But the $\log K_{\text{MAL}}$ values corresponding to the association of 5-fluorouracil, with $[\text{M-ADN}]^+$ are slightly lower (>1 log unit) than the $\log K_{\text{ML}}$ values (Table 2), the reason being that in $[\text{M-ADN}]^+$ species the M-N bond is influenced not only by L→M σ -interaction, but there also occurs to some extent M→L ($d\pi$ - $p\pi$) interaction which does not permit the concentration of electrons around the metal ions to increase significantly^{11,17}. On the other hand, formation/association of $[\text{M-ADN}]^+$ species with deprotonated 5-FU (L^{2-}) is also favoured due to coulombic attraction between the oppositely charged species and hence results in rather high stability of the mixed ligand complexes. Generally, metal-ADN complexes possess lower stability due to steric hindrance caused by the bulky ADN molecule, and stereochemical effects are more significant than electrostatic attraction between deprotonated ADN (A^-) and M(II) species.

Further, in binary as well as ternary Co^{II} systems, M-ADN, M : 5-FU and M : ADN : 5FU curves overlaps with ADN, 5-FU and M-ADN curves upto pH ~ 7.5, 8.5 and 6.5 respectively, and depart after that very little and subsequently precipitation occurs due to formation of hydroxo species. The $\log K$ values for all the three systems are lowest as compared with other cation complexes. Hence, it may be concluded that $[\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]^{2+}$ species is quite stable than Co^{II} -ADN/5-FU or Co^{II} -ADN-5FU mixed system.

A plot of $\log K_{\text{MAL}}$ vs $\log K_{\text{ML}}$ values is linear indicating that the process of association of 5-FU with $[\text{M-ADN}]^+$ in the ternary systems follows in general, the same pattern as that during the association of 5-FU with $[\text{M}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]^{2+}$ in the corresponding binary complexing systems.

Experimental

Solutions of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} nitrates (B.D.H., E. Merck) were prepared in distilled water and standardised¹⁸. The adenine (Aldrich) solution (0.01 M) was freshly prepared in NaOH solution, the final concentration of alkali being 0.02 M. A 0.01 M 5-fluorouracil (Aldrich) solution was prepared in distilled water. Stock solutions of sodium nitrate (1.0 M) and nitric acid (0.02 M) were used after standardisation. Carbonate-free NaOH (0.2 M) solution¹⁹ was standardised against potassium hydrogen phthalate solution and used as the titrant. All the reagents used were of AnalaR grade.

All the measurements were carried out at 25° using a Beckmann Φ 71 pH-meter. The six mixtures A, B, C, D, E and F were prepared and titrated separately against 0.2 M NaOH (CO_2 -free) bubbling N_2 in the cell during the titration : (A) HNO_3 (0.02 M, 5 ml) + NaNO_3 (1.0 M, 5.0 ml) + water; (B) HNO_3 (0.02 M, 10.0 ml) + NaNO_3 (1.0 M, 5.0 ml) + adenine (0.01 M, 5.0 ml) + water; (C) HNO_3 (0.02 M, 10.0 ml) + NaNO_3 (1.0 M, 5.0 ml) + adenine (0.01 M, 5.0 ml) + metal solution (0.01 M, 5.0 ml) + water; (D) HNO_3 (0.02 M, 5.0 ml) + NaNO_3 (1.0 M, 5.0 ml) + 5-

fluorouracil (0.01 M, 5.0 ml) + water; (E) HNO₃ (0.02 M, 5.0 ml) + metal solution (0.01 M, 5.0 ml) + water; (F) HNO₃ (0.02 M, 10.0 ml) + NaNO₃ (1.0 M, 5.0 ml) + adenine (0.01 M, 5.0 ml) + 5-fluorouracil (0.01 M, 5.0 ml) + metal solution + water. In each case, the total volume was maintained at 50 ml and ionic strength 0.1 M (NaNO₃).

For the titrations, the final concentrations were : 1.0×10^{-3} M metal ions, 1.0×10^{-3} M ligands primary (A : adenine) as well as secondary (L : 5-fluorouracil), 2.0×10^{-3} M nitric acid (HNO₃) and 0.1 M NaNO₃, in a total volume of 50 ml.

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